

MEMORANDUM

To The Clerk to the Committee, Committee on Constitutional, Legal & Parliamentary Affairs, Office of Parliament, Osu-Accra

From Ghana Studies Association (GSA)

Subject Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

Date September 23, 2021

The Ghana Studies Association (GSA), a multidisciplinary organization of scholars based at public and private universities in Ghana, North America, Europe, and Asia, and an International Affiliate of the African Studies Association (ASA), would like to register our explicit opposition to the proposed bill, Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values, currently under consideration in Parliament. The proposed bill is inherently and fundamentally unconstitutional and impinges on the Fundamental Human Rights and Freedoms of Ghanaians as stated in Article 12 (2) of the 1992 Constitution:

Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual in this Chapter but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest.

The bill seeks to criminalize Ghanaians based on their gender expressions and sexual identities, as well as any form of LGBTQI advocacy or support. If allowed to pass, the proposed bill will potentially lead to harmful consequences including violent rhetoric and action, and other forms of wrongful persecution of Ghanaians. The bill will also attract international opprobrium for Ghana, resulting in a loss of status as one of the most open-minded and attractive destinations for academic research on the continent. This could lead to a shortfall in funding for a variety of academic activities such as conferences, research collaborations, and student and faculty exchanges in the likely event that funding organizations and partner universities withdraw their support in protest of the proposed bill.

The GSA hereby calls on members of Parliament to reject the proposed bill.